

1 **Mesophotic Coral Ecosystems in the Eastern Tropical Pacific: The current**
2 **state of knowledge and the spatial variability of their depth boundaries**

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22 1. INTRODUCTION

23 Mesophotic ecosystems have attracted the attention of the scientific community over
24 the last two decades, especially the Mesophotic Coral Ecosystems (MCEs), because
25 of their potential to serve as a refuge for shallow coral communities affected by
26 thermal stress (Bongaerts et al., 2010; Glynn, 1996). These shallow communities
27 are degrading rapidly, mainly due to global climate change related impacts and
28 disturbances caused by human activities, such as over-fishing, tourism and coastal
29 development (Hughes et al., 2017; Spalding and Brown, 2015).

30 According to the definition of the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric
31 Administration (NOAA), MCEs are characterized by the presence of light-dependent
32 corals and associated communities, composed of other corals, sponges, and algae.

33 These ecosystems are typically found between 30-40 m and can extend down to
34 150 m in tropical and subtropical regions (Puglise et al., 2009). Although this
35 definition has been widely accepted, there exists an ongoing discussion regarding
36 the bathymetric boundaries of MCEs (Eyal et al., 2019; Laverick et al., 2020; Pyle
37 and Copus, 2019; Tamir et al., 2019).

38 Commonly, the upper mesophotic boundary has been defined for fixed depths
39 between 30 and 40 m, though this is more related to SCUBA diving limitations than
40 to ecology (Laverick et al., 2016) and it has been questioned, based on biological
41 evidence of changes from shallow to mesophotic coral reef communities at depths
42 as shallow as 10 m and as deep as 50 m, suggesting the use of a biological definition
43 of the upper mesophotic boundary rather than a fixed depth based on SCUBA
44 limitations (Laverick et al., 2017). On the other hand, the lower mesophotic boundary
45 is variable and defined by the deepest occurrence of light-dependent corals, which
46 relates to the water quality at the locations and the associated light attenuation within
47 the water column. Thus, the deepest records are found at locations with high optical
48 water quality, suggesting that light availability, i.e. PAR (photosynthetically active
49 radiation), represents one of the main factors defining MCEs lower boundaries
50 (Kahng et al., 2010). In this context, the diffuse light attenuation coefficient K_{dPAR} is
51 a parameter that characterizes the transparency of waters (Kirk, 2011) and hence,
52 can be used to calculate optical depths of particular interest, such as the 10% and
53 the 1% light level. These light levels are considered to be the midpoint and the
54 bottom of the euphotic zone, respectively (Kirk, 2011). Thus, several recent studies
55 proposed flexible depth limits to identify MCE boundaries, defined by available light

56 levels obtained from K_{dPAR} at a given location ($Z_{10\%}$, $Z_{1\%}$, $Z_{0.1\%}$), in combination with
57 coral community data (Eyal et al., 2019; Kahng et al., 2010; Laverick et al., 2020;
58 Lesser et al., 2018; Tamir et al., 2019).

59

60

61 In fact, a recent study provided a generalized light-driven model that can be used to
62 predict mesophotic depth boundaries, through a combination of community-light
63 relationships and underwater light field, defined by K_{dPAR} values (Laverick et al.,
64 2020). It also explains why at some locations mesophotic species and communities
65 have been recorded at depths as shallow as 10 m, as in these locations light
66 attenuation within the water column is high.

67 Furthermore, based on previous research on MCEs, a faunal transition has been
68 reported at approximately 60 m and used as a division between an upper mesophotic
69 subzone, a transition zone that includes shallow and mesophotic taxa, and the lower
70 mesophotic subzone, characterized by taxa adapted to low-light environment
71 (Kahng et al., 2019; Lesser et al., 2019, 2018). However, the fixed transition depth
72 at 60 m fails to explicitly accommodate the environmental variation at specific
73 locations (Laverick et al., 2017).

74 On a global scale, studies of MCEs have been conducted mainly in the Atlantic
75 region, Australia, the Red Sea, and Hawaii (Bongaerts et al., 2019; Eyal et al., 2021;
76 Pyle and Copus, 2019). Of those, 57% have been conducted in the Caribbean since

77 1966 (Turner et al., 2017). Despite the increasing research efforts worldwide, many
78 MCEs are still mostly unexplored, including those of the Eastern Tropical Pacific
79 (ETP) (Baker et al., 2016). The latter is also related to the general assumption that
80 MCEs are absent in the ETP, based on deep surveys in different locations within the
81 ETP and due to the characteristic permanent shallow thermocline that results in
82 marked differences between shallow and mesophotic conditions due to declines in
83 temperature and pH, as well as higher nutrient concentrations (Cortés et al., 2017).
84 The coral reef communities of the ETP extend from Baja California Sur, Mexico, to
85 the Gulf of Guayaquil in Ecuador and include the oceanic islands of Revillagigedo,
86 Clipperton, Cocos, Galapagos, Malpelo, and the Easter Island (Glynn et al., 2017).
87 These communities are exposed to seasonal upwelling events that affect water
88 transparency and other oceanographic characteristics, such as temperature, salinity,
89 and pH.

90 The ETP is characterized by a superficial thermocline with a commonly thin mixed
91 layer located between 10-30 m (Reyes-Bonilla and López-Pérez, 2009; Smith et al.,
92 2017). The region, with mean sea surface temperatures ranging from 20 to 29°C
93 (Shea et al., 1992), is influenced by seasonal coastal upwelling due to intense winds
94 bursts that prevail in the Gulfs of Tehuantepec, Papagayo, Panama between
95 November and April (Chapa-Balcorta et al., 2015; Kessler, 2006). The upwelling
96 events transport nutrients from deeper areas to the sea surface, generating seasonal
97 turbidity through algae blooms (García-Reyes and Largier, 2012).

98 Given the oceanographic characteristics of the ETP, light-dependent corals are
99 limited to shallow waters, which is why to date it is commonly assumed that MCEs
100 are absent in this region. However, recent evidence regarding the definition of MCEs,

101 based on optical depth boundaries, suggests that in locations with low light levels
102 due to high light attenuation, MCEs could be present as the so-called "shallow
103 turbidity reefs" (Laverick et al., 2020). Thus, in the present study, we performed a
104 systematic bibliographic revision of coral communities within the ETP and
105 subsequently, in combination with site-specific determinations of K_{dPAR} and derived
106 optical depths, identified the studies that can be considered MCE-related research
107 for this region. Furthermore, from the obtained database, we extracted coral
108 community data and assessed the current MCE research status in the ETP.

109 We used the optical depths ($z_{10\%}$, $z_{1\%}$, $z_{0.1\%}$) as markers of the mesophotic
110 boundaries, based on the evidence of some studies. For example, in the Red Sea
111 $z_{10\%}$ lies at 38 m ($K_d=0.06\text{ m}^{-1}$), matching the fauna transition at 40 m reported by
112 Tamir et al. (2019). Other examples are in the Caribbean Sea, which $z_{10\%}$ are at 38
113 m (Lesser et al., 2009). In general, in the clear waters where most MCE studies were
114 carried out, $z_{10\%}$ is close to 30-40 m and thus matches the upper boundary fixed by
115 NOAA definition. Similarly, the depth of $z_{1\%}$ is usually consistent with the general
116 fauna breakpoint at 60 m, though Laverick et al., (2020) considered $z_{0.1\%}$ as the lower
117 limit of the mesophotic zone because of the maximum depths records of light-
118 dependent corals in some places (Kahng et al., 2010; Laverick et al., 2020).
119 Therefore these optical depths represent a useful first approach to identify depth
120 ranges for the potential occurrence of MCEs in regions, where data for
121 geomorphology, community descriptions, and mesophotic indicator species are
122 scarce or absent.

123 Specifically, the goals of this review were to answer the following questions:

124 **Primary question:**

- 125 - What is the status of knowledge of coral systems in the ETP and their
126 respective community composition?

127 **Secondary questions:**

- 128 1. What are the mean values of K_{dPAR} within the ETP, and do they vary
129 spatially and/or seasonally?
- 130 2. What are the corresponding mesophotic optical depths ($Z_{10\%}$, $Z_{1\%}$, $Z_{0.1\%}$)?
- 131 3. What are the main research foci in mesophotic studies in the ETP?
- 132 4. Are there depth- and/or location-specific differences in the coral community
133 composition, depending on mesophotic depth boundaries (upper and lower
134 mesophotic zone)?
- 135 1. Do the maximum depth records of light-dependent corals show a
136 good correlation with location-specific water transparency (K_{dPAR}) and
137 hence, derived optical mesophotic boundaries?

138 **2. METHODS**

139 We performed a systematic review, using a search strategy adapted from other
140 studies of systematic research (Laverick et al., 2016; Turner et al., 2017). Two
141 independent and complementary search strings were carried out, followed by a
142 remote sensing analysis for each string (Fig. 1).

143

144 Fig. 1 Flowchart of the systematic bibliographic search and associated analyses.

145

146 The systematic search of scientific literature was performed using different digital
 147 databases.

148 In the first search string, we searched for diffuse attenuation coefficient (K_{dPAR}) or
 149 similar parameters (Secchi, euphotic depth values) for the ETP, to calculate the
 150 optical depths of mesophotic boundaries for the region. For the second search string,
 151 we searched for studies with information about benthic coral communities (corals
 152 and macroalgae) in the ETP. (See S1 file for detailed methods).

153

154 Only studies in English and Spanish were included, in which the search keywords
 155 appeared in the title, abstract or keywords, and grey literature and unavailable full
 156 texts were excluded.

157 The studies were screened in a two-stage process, according to the following
158 eligibility criteria (see also Fig. 1):

159 1) the title and the abstract were related to:

160 a. the subject in question

161 b. the study area was located in the ETP

162 2) for the full text:

163 a) Studies contained precise information to respond to the secondary
164 questions: *in situ* values of K_d and euphotic depths for the first set of
165 secondary questions (1 & 2), and species/genera composition and depth
166 for the next set of secondary questions (3 & 4).

167 b) Articles that contained relevant information (e.g., reports of species and
168 depths) from other references were replaced by the original sources.

169

170 After applying the eligibility criteria, the full-text documents were evaluated for
171 data extraction and quality assessment. The information was organized in a
172 spreadsheet by location, primary research topics (descriptive, taxonomy, review,
173 natural and anthropogenic impacts, life history, structuring variables, and
174 ecosystem function), following those described by Turner et al. (2017). The
175 information on corals and macroalgae was classified by country, depth, and
176 continental or oceanic locations. The species were clustered into four artificial
177 groups: macroalgae, light-dependent corals, gorgonians corals, and non-light-
178 dependent corals (mostly asymbiotic scleractinians, with a few reports of black and
179 soft corals). Subsequently, they were categorized by occurrence in either the upper

180 (z_{10%}- z_{1%}) or lower mesophotic zone (z_{1%} - z_{0.1%}), based on site-specific K_{D_{PAR}} and
181 derived mesophotic optical boundaries, obtained as described below.

182

183 *Remote sensing approach to define mesophotic boundaries based on optical depths*

184 To estimate the apparent optical properties of the ETP, we used time-averaged
185 maps and monthly time series of K_{d490} from the NASA's platform Giovanni: Goddard
186 Earth Sciences Data and Information Services Center
187 (<https://giovanni.gsfc.nasa.gov/>). The K_{d490} products of Giovanni were converted to
188 K_{D_{PAR}}, using the following equation (Morel et al., 2007):

$$189 \text{Kd}_{\text{PAR}} = 0.0864 + 0.884 \text{Kd}_{490} - 0.00137 [\text{Kd}_{490}]^{-1}$$

190 Using the QGIS software (QGIS, 2021), a time average map of K_{D_{PAR}} (Jan 2018-Oct
191 2020) was employed to regionalize the water transparency in the ETP and recover
192 the biotic composition according to five intervals of K_{D_{PAR}}: 0.03-0.0499, 0.05-0.074,
193 0.075-0.099, 0.1-0.1499, 0.15-0.1999.

194 For each category or K_{D_{PAR}} interval (K_{d1}-K_{d2}), the depths of the upper and lower
195 mesophotic light intervals were calculated, which for the purposes of this study
196 were defined as z_{10%} to z_{1%} and z_{1%} to z_{0.1%}, respectively:

197

$$198 \text{Kd}_{\text{PAR}} \text{ interval} = (\text{Kd}_1 - \text{Kd}_2)$$

$$199 \text{Upper mesophotic light interval} = (z_{10\%} - z_{1\%})$$

$$200 z_{10\%} = 2.3 / \text{Kd}_2$$

$$201 z_{1\%} = \frac{4.6}{(\text{Kd}_1 + \text{Kd}_2)/2}$$

$$202 \text{Lower mesophotic light interval} = ((z_{1\%} + 1) - z_{0.1\%})$$

$$203 z_{0.1\%} = 6.9 / \text{Kd}_1$$

204

205

206 Furthermore, based on the available maximum depth records of light-dependent
207 corals, found in the bibliographic search, the Kd_{490} time series (Aqua-MODIS
208 (<https://giovanni.gsfc.nasa.gov/>) for the continental and oceanic locations were
209 downloaded (January 2018 to January 2021) in the locations with the maximum
210 depth distribution of light-dependent corals.

211 Here, continental locations are considered those on the continental shelf, including
212 islands separated from the shelf by shallow and narrow arms of the sea. Oceanic
213 locations are represented by oceanic islands that arise from the bottom of the sea
214 as a result of the volcanic activity of the seabed, without connections to continental
215 landmasses, and generally located far from the continent and separated by large
216 depths (Fernández-Palacios and Morici, 2004).

217 The Kd_{490} time series were transformed to Kd_{PAR} as described above, and the values
218 were averaged for each location to obtain the corresponding site-specific optical
219 depths ($Z_{10\%}$, $Z_{1\%}$, $Z_{0.1\%}$), according to Kirk (2011). In addition, to verify the accuracy
220 of the satellite-derived data, we compared reported *in situ* Kd_{PAR} or Kd_{490} values with
221 those obtained from the MODIS-AQUA satellite data for the same location and, if
222 available, the same date.

223

224 2. RESULTS

225 2.1 *The state of MCE research in the ETP*

226 Seventy-seven papers were compiled in this study, covering the region of Loreto, in
227 Baja California Sur, Mexico, to Easter Island in Chile. The earliest study was
228 published in 1975, with a considerable increase in research efforts since 2000 (Fig.

229 2). Of all available studies, 49% were carried out in the continental zone, while 61%
230 were performed in oceanic regions, with eight studies covering both continental and
231 oceanic locations.

232

233

234 Fig. 2 Cumulative number of scientific publications over time, divided in studies at continental and
235 oceanic locations.

236

237 Some of the studies reviewed in this work were carried out in two or more countries
238 in the ETP, most of them in Costa Rica (20 papers), followed by Mexico and Panama
239 (Fig. 3B). In remote locations, like Easter and Clipperton islands, only a few research
240 studies are available (five or six studies).

241 Regarding the research focus of studies on MCEs in the ETP, ecosystem functions
242 have been studied in seven countries, while reviews are available for most countries.

243 Most MCE-related studies in the ETP available for continental locations focused on
244 taxonomy, reviews, and natural and anthropogenic impacts, with 34%, 15%, and
245 15%, respectively. Meanwhile, the research foci at oceanic locations were mostly
246 reviews (34%), as well as ecosystem functions (21%) and descriptive ecology (16%),

247 while only 4% of the studies were focused on biotic variables that structure the
 248 community along a depth gradient (Fig. 3A).

249

250

251 Figure 3. Overview of MCE-related studies in the ETP. A) Relative proportion of studies with specific
 252 research foci for oceanic and continental locations, and B) detailed by different countries of the ETP.

253

254 *2.2 Spatial K_{dPAR} variability in the ETP and the implications for mesophotic*
 255 *boundaries, based on optical depths*

256 In this review, we identified 51 locations along ETP, where research on mesophotic
 257 environments close to coral reefs have been carried out, concentrated much of them
 258 in turbidity continental waters (K_{dPAR} 0.1 - 0.2 m^{-1}) in the north of Mexico, Costa Rica,
 259 and Panamá (Fig. 4).

260 The water transparency was found to be highly variable within the ETP, being
 261 highest in the southern, oceanic region of the ETP, close to Easter Island
 262 (K_{dPAR} < 0.05 m^{-1}), and lowest along the coasts of Peru and Chile (K_{dPAR} > 0.2 m^{-1})
 263 and some areas of the Gulfs of California, Panama, Papagayo, and Tehuantepec.
 264 In the majority of the oceanic region, where islands like Clipperton, Cocos, and

265 Revillagigedo are located, the K_{dPAR} presents values between 0.05 and 0.1 m^{-1} . On
266 the other hand, most of the continental coastal zone within the ETP, as well as the
267 Galapagos and Malpelo Islands present mean K_{dPAR} values between 0.10 and 0.2
268 m^{-1} (Fig. 4).

269 Reports of *in situ* K_d measurements within the ETP are scarce, limited to Mexico,
270 Panama, and Easter Island. However, their comparison with K_d values, obtained
271 from satellite data, showed that there was general consistency between the two
272 approaches (Table S2).

273

274

275

276 Figure 4. Spatial variability of satellite-derived K_{dPAR} in the ETP, shown in the time average map of
277 K_{dPAR} downwelling irradiance (Jan 2018 to Oct 2020) (monthly 4 km resolution; MODIS-Aqua
278 L3m_Kd490 v2018). Locations with MCEs-related studies are indicated by brown circles and those
279 where deepest light-dependent corals records are available by green circles.

280

281 Considering the variability in water transparency within the ETP, we divided the
282 region of the ETP in 5 different categories, based on their K_{dPAR} range (Table 1).
283 Here, the oceanic region where the Easter island is located represents the highest
284 water transparency (hyperclear), followed by the oceanic region of the ETP (clear).
285 In contrast, the continental regions exhibit lower water transparency, with the highest
286 K_{dPAR} values registered for coastal regions under the influence of seasonal
287 upwelling. The derived optical depths for these regions ($K_{dPAR} > 0.1 \text{ m}^{-1}$; Table 1)
288 suggest that coral reefs there occurring at depths as shallow as 13-15 m could be
289 considered as mesophotic (or shallow turbid reefs).

290

291 Table 1. Water classification in the ETP, according to K_{dPAR} ranges (see Fig. 4) and the
292 derived mesophotic boundaries, based on optical depths

Transparency of water	Locations	Interval K_{dPAR} (m^{-1})	Upper mesophotic zone $Z_{10\%} - Z_{1\%}$ (m)	Lower mesophotic zone ($Z_{1\%} + 1$) - $Z_{0.1\%}$ (m)
Hyperclear	Easter and Salas y Gomez Is.	0.03-0.05	45-115	116-230
Clear 1	Revillagigedo Is.	0.05 – 0.074	30-74	75-140
Clear 2	Clipperton and Cocos Is.	0.075-0.099	25-50	51-90
Turbid 1	Malpelo and Galapagos Is. and continental locations	0.10 - 0.149	15-35	36-70
Turbid 2	Continental locations	0.15 - 0.199	13-25	26-45

293

294 *2.3 Benthic composition in the upper and lower mesophotic zone*

295

296 Based on the definition of mesophotic depth boundaries derived from site-specific
297 water transparency (see Table 1), we identified 51 locations within the ETP in our

298 bibliographic search, where research on mesophotic environments have been
299 carried out, with the majority concentrated in the north of Mexico, in Costa Rica and
300 Panamá (Fig. 4). In these studies, a total of 137 species were recorded in
301 mesophotic environments of the ETP; 21 of them were only identified at genera level:
302 19 taxa of macroalgae, 28 species of light-dependent corals, 62 species of
303 gorgonians, and 28 species of non-light-dependent corals (scleractinians corals,
304 black corals, soft corals) (see Table S2). In general, the species richness in the here
305 specified upper mesophotic zone, based on K_{dPAR} , was higher and decreased in the
306 lower mesophotic zone in both continental and oceanic locations (Fig. 5A). Also, the
307 number of macroalgal genera in the upper mesophotic zone was similar in the two
308 types of locations, while the species richness of light-dependent corals was higher
309 in oceanic, compared to the continental locations. In contrast, gorgonians showed a
310 higher number (4x) of species in continental locations. Likewise, in the lower
311 mesophotic zone, more gorgonian species were reported for continental locations,
312 while light-dependent corals were absent, with available records only for Clipperton
313 Island (Fig. 5B).

314 Also, for the oceanic islands, there was a notable difference in species richness in
315 Galápagos and Malpelo Islands, compared to the other islands (Fig. 5B).

316 Our revision resulted in reports of nine genera of light-dependent corals and 12
317 macroalgal genera in the upper mesophotic zone ($Z_{10\%}-Z_{1\%}$), while in the lower
318 mesophotic zone ($Z_{1\%+1}-Z_{0.1\%}$), only at Clipperton Island light-dependent corals of the
319 genus *Pavona* were reported (Table S2).

320

321

322

323 Figure 5. Cumulative species richness of different benthic groups in the upper and lower mesophotic
 324 zone at A) continental and oceanic locations, and B) at oceanic islands.

325

326 *2.4 Coral depth records and mesophotic boundaries*

327 The comparison of the mesophotic depth boundaries ($z_{10\%}$, $z_{1\%}$, and $z_{0.1\%}$), derived
 328 from the mean K_{dPAR} (Jan 2018-Dec 2020) at the different locations, where deepest
 329 records of light-dependent corals are available are shown in Figure 6. In general, as
 330 light attenuation decreased, the reported depth distribution of light-dependent corals
 331 increased in both continental locations and oceanic islands. The maximum depth for
 332 light-dependent coral distribution on the continental shelf has been reported between
 333 15-40 m, with the deepest record at 40 m for Cabo Pulmo, located in Baja California
 334 Sur, Mexico. This deepest record, together with those reported for Culebra Bay in
 335 Costa Rica and Puerto Angel, México, was consistent with $z_{1\%}$, calculated from site-
 336 specific K_{dPAR} . This pattern was also found for the oceanic locations Wenman Island
 337 in Galapagos, and Easter Islands (Fig. 6). The latter location registered the deepest
 338 light-dependent coral occurrence of the Eastern Pacific at 120 m, which agrees with

339 their extremely low K_{dPAR} values (Fig. 2, Table 1). Following the oceanic locations,
 340 the second deepest record was found at 80 m at Clipperton Island, but in this case,
 341 this depth corresponded to an optical depth of $\sim z_{0.1\%}$). On the other hand, the
 342 deepest occurrence of light-dependent corals for Socorro, Malpelo, and Gorgona
 343 Islands were recorded at depths that are close to $z_{10\%}$.
 344

345
 346
 347 Figure 6. A) Theoretical mesophotic light boundaries derived from K_{dPAR} ($z_{10\%}$ blue line, $z_{1\%}$
 348 red line, $z_{0.1\%}$ purple line) and the respective maximum depth records of light-dependent corals
 349 (green circles) in different location of the ETP). B) Derived mesophotic boundaries using
 350 K_{dPAR} values and light-dependent coral depth records reported by Kahng et al. (2010).
 351 Mesophotic boundaries at Jonson Atoll and Gambier Archipelago was derived using
 352 MODIS-AQUA.

353 Even with the notable variability in the apparent optical properties within the ETP,
 354 there was a strong correlation ($R^2=0.88$) between depth distribution of light-

355 dependent corals and the exponential decrease in light availability (Fig. 7B).
 356 Integrating our data with those previously reported for other regions Kahng et al.,
 357 (2010), they still show a strong exponential relationship ($R^2=0.82$) (Fig.7 B).
 358

359
 360 Figure 7. Exponential relationship between the maximum depth distribution of light-dependent corals
 361 with light attenuation coefficient (Kd_{PAR}). A) Kd_{PAR} and coral records, in the ETP (except
 362 Revillagigedo). Fitting function: Maximum coral depth = $2.73 * Kd_{PAR}^{-1.164}$ $R^2=0.88$, $p<0.05$, datapoint
 363 for Revillagigedo Islands (white circle) was considered an outlier and excluded from the analysis. B)
 364 Integrating Kd_{PAR} and coral records in the ETP, plus the data reported by (Kahng et al., 2010)
 365 including different locations in the Caribbean, the Red Sea, and Hawaii (pink dots). Fitting function:
 366 Maximum coral depth = $1.91 * Kd_{PAR}^{-1.34}$ $R=0.82$.

367 3. DISCUSSION

368
 369 *The current state of MCE research in the ETP*

370 Studies on MCEs have increased considerably over the last decade, from 200 to
 371 more than 600 studies, though these include only a few studies in the ETP
 372 (Bongaerts et al., 2019). However, considering the theoretical mesophotic

373 boundaries based on light availability, as defined in the present study, we were able
374 to account for a total of 77 studies in mesophotic environments in the ETP.
375 Nevertheless, this region is greatly understudied, compared to the Tropical Western
376 Atlantic and the Indo-Pacific, which account for 444 and 245 mesophotic studies,
377 respectively (Eyal et al., 2021). This difference could be related to the general
378 assumption that MCEs should be absent in most of the ETP, based on the upper
379 mesophotic boundary of NOAA's definition, and since the oceanographic conditions
380 of the ETP are limiting the development of light-dependent coral communities below
381 30 m in most locations. As a result, less than ten studies from the ETP contain the
382 term "mesophotic" to date. Likewise, the relatively few studies in the ETP could be
383 associated to the limited research infrastructure in the mostly developing countries
384 of this region. Also, 33 studies have been conducted in continental areas, while 26
385 have been carried out at oceanic locations. This difference might be related to the
386 lack of resources and potential difficulties regarding access to those remote islands.
387 Moreover, our revision shows that most of MCE research in the ETP has been so
388 far focused on taxonomy and reviews, while studies on other topics, which are well-
389 studied in other regions, such as community structure, molecular ecology (Bongaerts
390 et al., 2019), are extremely scarce.

391

392 *3.1 Spatial K_{dPAR} variability in the ETP and the implications for mesophotic* 393 *boundaries*

394 Our selected water classification categories showed that there is a wide range of
395 water transparency (K_{dPAR}) within the ETP and thus, this region represents an

396 excellent case study of assessing the accurateness of using mesophotic boundaries,
397 based on light availability, and the presence of light-dependent corals.

398 The oceanic region is the most likely place where MCEs could develop in the ETP,
399 falling into the categories hyperclear, clear 1, and clear 2. These three types of
400 waters present K_{dPAR} values within the range of the locations where most MCEs
401 studies have been carried out (0.045 to 0.08 m^{-1}) (Kahng et al., 2010; Laverick et al.,
402 2017; Lesser et al., 2018; Tamir et al., 2019). However, our work shows that
403 locations within the ETP that are influenced by upwelling events and thus exhibit
404 higher K_{dPAR} values (0.1-0.2 m^{-1}), where light-dependent corals are present within
405 the defined mesophotic boundaries ($Z_{10\%}$ - $Z_{0.1\%}$) might be considered MCEs (shallow
406 turbid reefs), as also recently suggested by Laverick et al. (2020).

407 Our approach of defining MCEs based on light levels raises the following question:
408 what is the minimum value of water transparency for an ecosystem to be considered
409 MCEs? What is the minimum depth for a mesophotic ecosystem? For responding to
410 this question, we have to remember Glynn's (1996) hypothesis: "deep-sea corals
411 can act as thermal refuges for shallow-water corals reefs". Now the question is, what
412 is the initial depth of deep-sea corals?

413 Based on the present study, in the ETP corals can be referred to as mesophotic
414 when occurring at depth close to 10 m, due to the oceanographic conditions in the
415 region (seasonal upwelling events) that make it possible to find relatively shallow
416 refugia in this region. Smith et al. (2017) distinguished in the ETP some potential
417 zones for depth-refugia, mostly at oceanic islands, including some places in
418 continental areas, like the Gulf of Chiriquí, where a depth refugia of *Millepora*

419 *intricata* was found at 25 m (Smith et al., 2017). The information above supports why
420 our research considers only waters with a maximum K_{dPAR} value of 0.199, which
421 return an upper mesophotic boundary at 12 m.

422 Even using the most common K_{dPAR} range for MCE, the difference in the K_{dPAR}
423 values of those clear waters is large, resulting in enormous differences in the lower
424 mesophotic boundaries. For example, the deepest record of light-dependent corals
425 is currently at 172 m at Gambier archipelago (Rouzé et al., 2021), which present a
426 $K_{dPAR}=0.04\text{ m}^{-1}$, while in Clipperton Island, with a K_{dPAR} of 0.081 m^{-1} , the maximum
427 coral record is at 80 m, but represent almost the same optical depth as the former
428 location ($z_{0.1\%}$) (Fig. 6B).

429 Considering that the maximum depth of light-dependent corals is the conditional
430 factor of the lower limit of MCEs, together with mesophotic boundaries ($z_{10\%}$ - $z_{0.1\%}$),
431 our results contrast the following. For example, at Wenman islands (Galápagos), the
432 mesophotic zone extends to 40 m. However, the presence of coral communities has
433 been reported at 20 m, which is close to $z_{1\%}$ (Fig. 6). However, in Malpelo, with
434 similar water transparency, these corals have only been reported up to 27m, which
435 leaves only 7m of the water column to develop MCEs. It should be noted that in
436 these oceanic locations, the study area by the authors are explored intensively by
437 Peter Glynn in Galapagos and Zapata y Vargas in Malpelo Island, Colombia.

438 *3.2 Benthic composition*

439 The transition from shallow to mesophotic reefs does not occur at a specific depth,
440 but rather depends on location-specific factors, such as water clarity, temperature,

441 substrate type, water currents, topography, among others (Costa et al., 2015).
442 However, light is the primary factor in controlling the bathymetric structure of
443 photosynthetic communities (Lesser et al., 2009; Tamir et al., 2019).
444 The species richness compiled during this investigation reflects an acceptable notion
445 of the components of MCEs. The species composition of mesophotic environments
446 of the ETP presents differences between the upper mesophotic and the lower
447 mesophotic zone, with a general reduction in the species richness of autotrophs in
448 the lower mesophotic zone. In the continental locations and some oceanic islands
449 with upwelling events, light-dependent corals can be found between 15 m and 40 m
450 corresponding to the upper mesophotic light interval ($Z_{10\%}$ - $Z_{1\%}$), while the lower
451 mesophotic light interval ($Z_{1\%}$ - $Z_{0.1\%}$) is dominated by CCAs, gorgonians and non-
452 light-dependent corals. The oceanic and continental locations present a similar
453 community composition in the upper mesophotic zone, while in the lower mesophotic
454 there are more macroalgal species and non-light-dependent corals in oceanic
455 locations. Furthermore, only at Clipperton island light-dependent corals were found
456 along the entire mesophotic zone down to $\sim Z_{0.1\%}$.

457

458 *3.3 Other variables involved in limiting MCEs*

459 Even though there is a strong correlation between maximum coral records and light
460 attenuation (Fig. 7), other oceanographic conditions can limit the bathymetric
461 distribution of these corals above $Z_{1\%}$ or even close to $Z_{10\%}$, as in the cases of
462 Gorgona, Malpelo, and Revillagigedo islands. The last location belongs to category
463 Clear 1 in the ETP ($K_{dPAR}=0.065 \text{ m}^{-1}$), though the maximum depth distribution of

464 light-dependent corals is reported at only 33 m (Ketchum and Reyes-Bonilla, 2001).
465 This bathymetric restriction has been suggested to be related to a seasonally
466 changing thermocline that occur at 25 m in September, descending to 70 m between
467 January and March, in conjunction with internal waves (Carter et al., 2020).

468 On the other hand, at Cocos Island the reported maximum depths for light-
469 dependent corals are close to 40 m (Cortés, 2019), which lies between the optical
470 mesophotic boundaries of $z_{10\%}$ and $z_{1\%}$ (Fig. 6). This might be related to the generally
471 shallow thermocline, which has been reported to be at approximately 50 m depth at
472 Cocos Island (Cortés, 2019). Indeed, at Cocos Island a pronounced difference
473 between benthic communities above and below the thermocline at 50 m depth has
474 been reported, possibly as a result of drastic changes in light availability due to the
475 accumulation of particulate matter at the thermocline (Cortés, 2019).

476

477 *3.4 Advantage and weakness of KdPAR-derived satellite data*

478 In the ETP, published research on the apparent *in situ* optical properties of the water
479 column and the underwater light environment is scarce and available only for a few
480 locations.

481 This region presents very low K_{dPAR} values (Fig. 4, Table 2) that were similar
482 between our estimations from MODIS-Aqua remote sensing and the values reported
483 by Morel et al. (2007), derived from hyperspectral (downward and upward) irradiance
484 measurements.

485

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